

CONSTRUCTIVISM AND EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The Aim of this paper is to identify Constructivist approach connected with teaching and learning in a social environment. This paper describes “what is constructivism?” and constructivism’s principles, There is try to explain environment of constructivism and interaction between task, instructor and learner. The aim of this paper is that we can make a student the investigator, thinker and decision maker etc. with the help of constructivism.

Key words: *Constructivist Approach In Teaching And Learning.*

What is Constructivism?

Constructivism is a theory to explain how knowledge is constructed in the human being when information comes into contact with existing knowledge that had been developed by experiences. It has its roots in cognitive psychology and biology and an approach to education that lays emphasis on the ways knowledge is created in order to adapt to the world. Constructs are the different types of filters we choose to place over our realities to change our reality from chaos to order.

Constructivism: “a theory of knowledge with roots in philosophy, psychology, and cybernetics”. Constructivism has implications for the theory of instruction Discover, hands-on experiential, collaborative project-based and task-based learning are a number of applications that base teaching and learning on constructivism.

Constructivism is a view of learning based on the belief that knowledge isn't a thing a can be simply given by the teacher at the front of the room to students In their desks. Rather,

knowledge is constructed by learners through an active, mental process of development: learners are the builders and creators of meaning and knowledge.

Constructivist Learning:

Constructivist learning has emerged as a prominent approach to teaching during this past decade. The work of Dewey, Montessori, Piaget, Burner, and Vygotsky among others provides historical precedents for Constructivist learning theory. Constructivism represents a paradigm shift from education based on behaviorism to education based on cognitive theory. Behaviorist epistemology focuses on intelligence, domains of objectives, levels of knowledge, and reinforcement. Constructivist epistemology assumes that learners construct their own knowledge on the basis of the interaction with their environment.

Four epistemological assumptions are at the heart of what we refer to as “Constructivist learning.”

1. Knowledge is physically constructed by learners who are involved in active learning.
2. Knowledge is symbolically constructed by learners who are making their own representations of action:
3. Knowledge is socially constructed by learners who convey their meaning making to others.
4. Knowledge is theoretically constructed by learners who try to explain things they don't completely understand.

Constructivist Teaching and Learning :

Constructivist teaching is based on the belief that learning occurs as learners are actively involved in a process of meaning and knowledge construction rather than passively receiving information. Learners are the makers of meaning and knowledge. Constructivist teachings foster critical thinking and create motivated and independent learners.

A Constructivist teacher and a Constructivist classroom are distinguished from a traditional teacher and classroom by a number of identifiable qualities: the learners are actively involved: the environment is democratic: the activities are interactive and student-centered: and

the teacher facilitates a process of learning in which students are encouraged to be responsible and autonomous.

Constructivist learning environments:

1. Constructivist learning environment provide multiple representations of reality.
2. Multiple representations avoid over simplifications and represent the complexity of the real world.
3. Constructivist learning environments emphasize knowledge construction instead of knowledge reproduction.
4. Constructivist learning environments emphasize authentic tasks in a meaningful context rather than abstract instruction out of context.
5. Constructivist learning environments provide learning environments such as real-world settings or case-based learning instead of predetermined sequences of instruction.
6. Constructivist learning environment encourage thoughtful reflection on experience.

Interaction between task, instructor and learner:

A further characteristic of the role of the facilitator in the social Constructivist viewpoint is that the instructor and the learners are equally involved in learning from each other as well. This means that the learning experience is both subjective and objective and requires that the instructors' culture, values and background become an essential part of the interplay between learners and tasks. Learners compare their version of the truth with that of the instructor and fellow learners to get to a new, socially tested version of truth. The task or problem is thus the interface between the instructor and the learner. This creates a dynamic interaction between task, instructor and learner. This entails that learners and instructors should develop an awareness of each other's viewpoints. This entails that learners and instructors should develop an awareness of each other's viewpoints and then look to their own belief, standards and values, thus being both subjective and objective at the same time.

Some learning approaches that could harbor this interactive learning include reciprocal teaching, peer collaboration, cognitive apprenticeship, problem-based instruction, web quests, anchored instruction and other approaches that involve learning with others.

Importance of Constructivism:

Educational curricula and teaching methods are changing. One component of the current development of all subject area curricula is the change in focus of instruction from the transmission curriculum to a transactional curriculum. In a traditional curriculum, a teacher transmits information students who passively listen to acquire facts, in a transactional curriculum, students are actively involved in their learning to reach new understandings.

A Constructivist approach is used to create learners who are autonomous, inquisitive thinkers who question, investigate and reason. A Constructivist approach frees teachers to make decisions that will enhance and enrich students "Development" in these areas.

Conclusion:

A Constructivist approach is truly learner centered approach. In the present world of information and communication technology information is just at one click but we have to convert this information into knowledge Constructivist approach, in a real sense given the freedom of learning experiment projects, field work analytical & creative thinking develops knowledge gives birth to innovations. Because of constructivist approach role of teacher has also changed teacher is a mentor, take form of teacher. With the application of approach we can fill the gap of life & education as a result when these learners will they will enrich those areas, professions.

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